

EFFECT OF LOW TEMPERATURE ON SELF HEALING PERFORMANCE OF CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITES

Mohammad Asgar-Khan¹ and Suong Van Hoa²

Department of Mechanical and Industrial Engineering, Concordia University
Montreal, Quebec, H3G 1M8, Canada

¹Email: warsi94536@yahoo.com,

²Email: hoasuon@alcor.concordia.ca

Keywords: Self healing, Composites, Cold temperature, Space, Mode II fracture test

ABSTRACT

Most of the studies of self healing of Fiber Reinforced Polymer Composites (FRPC) involve different types of monomer and resin systems which are not suitable for space applications. Ethylene Norbornene (ENB) monomer, on the other hand, was found to be a potential monomer candidate for this purpose due to its low freezing point temperature and fast cure kinetics. The current work thus explores the monomer as self healing agent for FRPC for space applications. Microcapsules containing liquid 5E2N monomer in poly melamine urea formaldehyde (PMUF) shells have been synthesized following the in-situ emulsion polymerization technique. Epoxy resin modified with microcapsules and catalysts are infused between the layers of unidirectional carbon fabric to manufacture FRPC using hand lay-up with autoclave molding. Two types of FRPC specimens were fabricated. One is neat regular carbon/epoxy composites without any healing agents (microcapsules and catalysts). The other type of carbon/epoxy composites is fabricated by using resins modified with microcapsules containing 5-Ethylidene-2-Norbornene (5E2N) and Grubbs catalyst. Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness of the specimens are determined for the NPC (no precrack) and PC (precrack) configurations as described in the ASTM WK22949 protocol. A simple equation incorporating the NPC and PC fracture toughness of the regular and modified specimen is established to provide a healing performance index capable of indicating and comparing the quality of healing. The equation also accounts for the effect on the base properties due to the inclusion of the healing agents. An environment chamber enclosing the test fixtures, fed with liquid nitrogen and with the facility of controlling the temperature is used to maintain the low temperature during the test and healing period. The fracture tests were carried out at room temperature and low temperature (-40°C) conditions. The healing performance index and healing efficiency of the FRPC is compared at room temperature and low temperature.

1 INTRODUCTION

Most of the modern satellites launched into earth orbit, and even some manned spacecraft are constructed with specially designed composite panels as their primary load bearing elements [1]. They also serve as the protection systems for the internal critical parts like fuel tank, precision devices and sensitive equipment like optical sensors, mirrors etc. [2]. One of the major concerns involving the use of fiber reinforced composites as spacecraft structure is their susceptibility to hypervelocity impact caused by natural micrometeoroids and man-made space debris with a wide range of sizes and velocities. These damages can vary from very severe (where holes are punctured through the structure) to minor damages (where small dents are made into the structure). Damages in space structures can shorten their lives. In-service manual repair may be carried out but at a great cost. One preferable scenario would be to provide self healing capability to the structure. Most of the composite self healing studies to date, however, involve healing at room temperature or higher. The current work thus investigates the effect of low temperature which prevails in space environment, on self healing of carbon/epoxy composites.

Dicylopentadiene (DCPD)/Grubbs catalyst based microencapsulated healing system has been investigated extensively by the group of White and coworkers [3, 4-13]. DCPD having a freezing point around 10 °C is not suitable for space applications. One of the requirements of healing agent to be used

in space is that the healing agent must remain liquid at the low temperatures prevailing in space. Lee et al. [14] observed that 5E2N, compared to DCPD, have advantages as a healing agent because, when cured under same conditions as DCPD, it reacts much faster in the presence of a much lower amount of catalyst, has very low freezing point, and produces a resin that has a higher value of glass transition temperature (T_g). The characteristics of the low freezing point and high reactivity of 5E2N are thus suitable for its application in space. Microencapsulated 5E2N/Grubbs catalyst system is thus studied at low temperature in this work.

Different methods are employed by different groups of researchers for measuring the healing efficiency. In most of the works [4-5, 9-11, 15-19], mode I fracture toughness was compared before and after healing to determine the healing efficiency. Beside the mode I fracture toughness, residual compressive strength after impact [20], peak loads and strain energy in three point bending [21] and the residual flexural strength after impact [22] were also compared in various investigations to determine the healing efficiency for both resin only and FRPC samples. As the study of healing in composites involves crack, it might be more appropriate to analyze it based on fracture mechanics approach rather than strength of materials approach. Thus, comparing the fracture toughness in determining healing efficiency might reflect direct contribution of healing. While, mode I type crack propagation is common during interlaminar fracture of laminated composites, mode II fracture is also a major matrix-controlled failure mode induced by out of plane shear stresses frequently encountered in composite structures. As a fundamental failure mode, mode II delamination strongly influences a wide range of structural behavior under out-of-plane loading, especially that due to surface loading such as impact [23]. Thus, in the current work, healing performance is evaluated by measuring the mode II fracture toughness in NPC and PC configurations for regular (without healing agents) and modified (with healing agents) carbon/epoxy composite specimens at low temperature (-40C).

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Synthesis of microcapsules containing 5E2N

Synthesis of microcapsules having poly melamine urea formaldehyde (PMUF) shells containing 5E2N liquid monomer has been carried out using in situ emulsion polymerization technique described in [24]. A good quality batch of microcapsules should be free flowing (non sticky), having intended average size, narrow size distribution, more than 80% monomer content and be thermally stable up to certain temperatures. Microcapsules of average sizes ranging from 20 to 200 μm have been successfully produced. Control on the quality of microcapsules were principally achieved by varying the stirring speed, amount and concentration of surfactant and emulsifying agent and the washing/filtering method. The quality of microcapsules was characterized using Optical microscope (OM), Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) and Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA).

Figure 1. Microcapsules containing 5E2N in PMUF shells

2.2 Fabrication of specimen

The healing agents (microcapsules and catalyst particles) are dispersed in epoxy (EPON 828) and curing agent (Epicure 3046) using a vacuum centrifugation method. The modified epoxy is used to make the two layers that make up the interface of the 12 layer unidirectional carbon fabric using hand lay-up method. Regular epoxy (without the healing agents) is applied to other layers. A thin teflon film is inserted at the mid-layer interface which acts as a starter pre-crack during the NPC test described later. The lay-up is then vacuum bagged and put into autoclave for curing. Vacuum, pressure and temperature were set to the intended level during curing. After curing and post curing, the sample is cut into desired dimensions according to ASTM WK22949 for the mode II fracture test using a diamond cutter.

2.3 Test set up

The specimens are loaded into a three point bending fixture attached with the required extensions. The entire fixture with the extensions are inserted into an environmental chamber equipped with liquid nitrogen flow facility and temperature controller. The fixture is then attached to the MTS machine. Liquid nitrogen cylinder is attached to the environmental chamber. The test set up is shown in figure 2. When the temperature reaches to the desired level and becomes stable, test procedure starts. Load-displacement data is recorded continuously during the test for later analysis.

Figure 2. a) Environmental chamber enclosing the fixtures in the MTS machine, and attached to liquid nitrogen supply. b) 3-point bending fixtures holding the composite samples inside the environmental chamber and extensions attached to MTS machine

2.4 Test procedure

Mode II fracture toughness is measured using a compliance calibration method described in [25]. The specimens are arranged in the three point bending fixture according to the arrangements in figure 3. For the NPC test, one end of the teflon insert acts as the starter precrack tip. The crack length is measured from the left support roller to the crack tip. This crack length is kept the same for the subsequent PC test. After the 1st loading, the crack extends from the end of the Teflon insert. After the NPC loading, the sample is unloaded and kept in a dry ice chamber maintained at -40 °C for 24 hours to allow for healing. During the 2nd loading (PC test), the sample is repositioned to keep the new crack tip at a same distance from the left support roller (Figure 3b). Healing performance is then evaluated by calculating the fracture toughness calculated according to data reduction procedure described in [25].

Figure 3. Schematic configuration and relative position of specimen on three point bending fixture for the fracture test a) NPC configuration and b) PC configuration

2.4 Healing performance

Self healing performance is evaluated using the following equations:

$$PI = \eta_h - \Delta\varphi \quad (1)$$

Where

PI refers to Performance Index of healing

η_h refers to healing efficiency and

$\Delta\varphi$ refers to index of change in base property

$$\eta_h = \frac{(G_{II,PC}^c)_M - (G_{II,PC}^c)_R}{(G_{II,NPC}^c)_R - (G_{II,PC}^c)_R} \quad (2)$$

and

$$\Delta\varphi = \frac{(G_{II,NPC}^c)_R - (G_{II,NPC}^c)_M}{(G_{II,NPC}^c)_R} \quad (3)$$

Here,

G_{II}^c refers to strain energy release rates measured during the NPC and PC tests, and

R and M refer to regular (without healing agents) and modified (with healing agents) samples respectively.

Here, $\Delta\phi$ represents the change in the base property due to the inclusion of the healing agents into the regular sample. This term is subtracted from the healing efficiency term η_h to represent the overall improvement in fracture performance of the modified sample compared to regular sample due to healing.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FRPC Samples are made with regular epoxy resin (without microcapsules and catalyst) and modified epoxy resin (incorporated with microcapsules and catalyst). Specimens are tested in NPC and PC configurations at room temperature and cold (-40 °C) temperature conditions. In table 1, the types, configuration and temperature at which specimens are tested are illustrated and the measured values of the fracture toughness are listed. At least 3 replicates were tested for each series.

Sample series	Configuration	Concentration of microcapsules (%)	Average size of microcapsules (μm)	Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	GII ^c (J/m^2)	Standard deviation
A (Reg)	NPC	0	-	RT	2450	237
	PC	0	-	RT	1172	210
B (Mod)	NPC	2	100	RT	2026	65
	PC	2	100	RT	1609	51
C (Mod)	PC	2	40	-40	1726	27

Table 1. Types of samples, test conditions and measured fracture toughness

Samples A contain no healing agents, i.e. no microcapsules and catalysts. It is termed here as regular (reg) samples. Samples B and C contain 2 weight percent of microcapsules and generally termed here as modified (mod) samples. Samples of each type were tested with NPC and PC configurations. For sample C, the NPC values obtained from the measurement are not accepted due to its large scatter and is not listed in table 1. For the purpose of calculating healing efficiency, it is assumed to be equal to the NPC value of sample B which contains the same weight percentage of microcapsules. The results are summarized in figure 4.

Figure 4. Summary of the results of mode II fracture test

Using the available data and equations (1), (2) and (3) the healing efficiency and healing performance index are calculated and compared between room temperature and cold (-40°C) temperature conditions. It is found that, for room temperature, healing efficiency (η_h) for sample B is 34%. Whereas, healing performance values (PI) for the sample is only 17%. As an example, for sample B, from table 1, we get,

$$\begin{aligned} (G_{II,NPC}^C)_M &= 2026 \text{ J/m}^2 \\ (G_{II,PC}^C)_M &= 1609 \text{ J/m}^2 \end{aligned}$$

For regular sample, from table 1, we get,

$$\begin{aligned} (G_{II,NPC}^C)_R &= 2450 \text{ J/m}^2 \\ (G_{II,PC}^C)_R &= 1172 \text{ J/m}^2 \end{aligned}$$

Putting these values in equations (3), (2) and (1), we get, for sample B,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Healing efficiency, } \eta_h &= 34\% \text{ and} \\ \text{Performance Index, } PI &= 17\% \end{aligned}$$

This means that although the healing efficiency value η_h is high for sample B, they show only 17% better performance compared to regular (without healing agents) sample A. Similarly, at cold temperature, the values of healing efficiency and healing performance are 43% and 26% respectively for sample C. Comparing the values of healing efficiency and healing performance index, it can be concluded that, sample C (2wt%, 40 μm average size) at cold temperature shows better healing performance than sample B (2wt%, 100 μm average size) at room temperature.

SEM micrographs of the fracture surfaces of the samples B and C are shown in figures 5 (a) and (b).

Figure 5. SEM micrographs of the fracture surface of FRPC samples after mode II fracture test at a) sample B at room temperature and b) sample C at cold temperature (-40 °C)

Matrix cracking and fiber-matrix debonding are found to be the principal modes of damage at both room temperature and cold temperature. Some microcapsules are also observed to be dislodged from the matrix surface during the crack propagation. Hackle marking and cleaner exposed fiber surface are observed in sample B while striations and less exposed fiber surface are observed in sample C. However, the difference cannot be attributed to the size of the microcapsules or cold temperature. Further study should identify the effect of these two factors.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Regular (without healing agents) and modified (with healing agent) FRPC samples are tested for measuring the mode II fracture toughness at room temperature and at -40°C. An equation is proposed to calculate the healing efficiency and healing performance index taking into account the effect of incorporating healing agents into the regular samples. Samples containing 2 wt%, 40 μm average size microcapsules at cold temperature show better healing performance than sample containing 2wt%, 100

µm average size microcapsules at room temperature. Efforts are underway to obtain more data points and fracture surface images at room temperature and cold temperature for determining the optimum healing performance and the underlying reasons for the variations in healing performances.

REFERENCES

- [1] Wicklein, M., Ryan, S. White, D. and Clegg, R. , Hypervelocity impact on CFRP: Testing, material modeling, and numerical simulation, *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, **35**, 2008, 1861-1869
- [2] Grujicic, M, Pandurangan, B, Zhao, C., Biggers, S. and Morgan, D., Hypervelocity impact resistance of reinforced carbon-carbon/carbon-foam thermal protection systems, *Applied Surface Science*, **252**, 2006, 5035-5050.
- [3] White, S., Sottos, N., Geubelle, P., Moore, J., Kessler, M., Sriram, S., Brown, E. and Viswanathan, S., Autonomic healing of polymer composites, *Nature*, **409**, 2001, p 794-817
- [4] Keller, M. and Sottos, N., Effect of Microcapsule Properties on Self-Healing Composite Performance, *Proceedings of the 2004 SEM X International Congress on Experimental and Applied Mechanics*, 2004
- [5] Brown, E, White S, Sottos, N, Microcapsules induced toughening in a self healing polymer composite, *Journal of Materials Science*, **39**, 2004, p 1703-1710
- [6] Brown, E, White S, Sottos, N, Fracture Testing of a Self-Healing Polymer Composite, *Experimental mechanics*, **42** (4), 2002, p 373-379
- [7] Rule, J., Sottos, N. and White, S., Effect of microcapsule size on the performance of self-healing polymers, *Polymer*, **48**, 2007, p 3520-3529
- [8] Brown, E, Use of the tapered double-cantilever-beam geometry for fracture toughness measurements and its application to the quantification of self-healing, *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Self Healing Materials, Bath, UK, 2011*, p 87-88
- [9] Kirkby, E., Rule, J., Michaud, V., Sottos, N., White, S. and Manson, J., Embedded shape-memory alloy wires for improved performance of self-healing polymers, *Advanced Functional Materials*, **18**, 2008, p 2253–2260
- [10] Kessler, M. and White, S., Self activated healing of delamination damage in woven composites, *Composites: Part A*, **32**, 360–368, 2001
- [11] Kessler, M., Sottos, N. and White, S., Self-healing structural composite materials, *Composites: Part A*, **34**, 2003, 743-753
- [12] Patel, A., Sottos, N., Wetzel, E. and White, S., Autonomic healing of low-velocity impact damage in fiber-reinforced composites, *Composites: Part A*, **41**, 360–368, 2010
- [13] O'Brien T. and White S., Assesment of composite delamination self-healing via micro-encapsulation. In: *American society for composites 23rd technical conference proceedings. Memphis, (TN, USA), 2008*, DEStech Publications, Inc., p. 116–35
- [14] Lee, J., Hong, S., Liu, X. and Yoon, S., Characterization of dicyclopentadiene and 5-ethylidene-2-norbornene as self-healing agents for polymer composite and its microcapsules, *Macromolecular Research*, **12** (5), 2004, p 478-483
- [15] Yin, T., Rong, M., Zhang, M. and Yang, G., Self-healing epoxy composites – preparation and effect of the healant consisting of microencapsulated epoxy and latent curing agent, *Composites Science and Technology*, **67**, 2007, p 201–212
- [16] Sanada, K., Mizuno, Y. and Shindo, Y., Notched tensile tests and analysis of unidirectional fiber composites encompassing self-healing of interfacial debonding, *Proceeding of the Third International Conference on Self Healing Materials (3ICSHM), Bath, UK, 2011*
- [17] Chen, X., Dam, M., Ono, K., Mal, A., Shen, H., Nutt, S., Sheran, K. and Wudl, F., A thermally re-mendable cross-linked polymeric material, *Science*, **295**, 2002, p 1698-1702

- [18] Chen, X., Wudl, F., Mal, A., Shen, H., and Nutt, S., New thermally remendable highly cross-linked polymeric materials, *Macromolecules*, **36**, 2003, p 1802-1807
- [19] Varley, R. and Parn, G., Thermally activated healing in a mendable resin using a non woven EMAA fabric, *Composites Science and Technology*, **7**, 2012, p 453–460
- [20] Belay, S., Loader, C., Hawyres, V., Humberstone, L. and Curtis, P., A smart repair system for polymer matrix composites, *Composites: Part A*, **32**, 2001, p 1767-1776
- [21] O'Brien T. and White S., Assesment of composite delamination self-healing via micro-encapsulation. In: *American society for composites 23rd technical conference proceedings. Memphis, (TN, USA): DEStech Publications, Inc., 2008, p. 116–35*
- [22] Pang, J. and Bond, I., 'Bleeding composites'—damage detection and self-repair using a biomimetic approach, *Composites: Part A*, **36**, 2005, p 183–188
- [23] Lee, S., Mode II delamination failure mechanisms of polymer matrix composites, *Journal of Material Science*, **32(5)**, 1997, p 1287-1295
- [24] Liu, X., Sheng, X., Lee, J., Kessler, M., Synthesis and Characterization of Melamine-Urea-Formaldehyde Microcapsules Containing ENB-Based Self-Healing Agents, *Macromolecular Materials and Engineering*, **294**, 2009, p 389-395
- [25] Davidson, B. and Teller, S., Recommendations for an ASTM standardized test for determining GIIC of unidirectional laminated polymeric matrix composites, *Journal of ASTM International*, **7(2)**, Article ID JAI102619, 2010